

OXYFUEL – COMBUSTION

Reduce your fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions through efficient high-temperature processes

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF OXYFUEL TECHNOLOGY FOR MY COMPANY?

Fuel savings

Reduction of CO₂ emissions

Cost savings

Potential for CO₂ capture and utilisation

WHAT ARE THE REQUIREMENTS FOR MY PROCESSES?

- ✓ The greatest efficiency improvements occur at high process and exhaust temperatures.
- ✓ Oxyfuel technology requires the use of oxygen. Ideally, there is already an O₂ supply at your site.
- ✓ When using Oxyfuel technology, a flue gas composition is generated that facilitates CO₂ capture. In the best case, the CO₂ can be used internally in the operation.

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Set-up an initial consultation appointment with the NEFI team!

Step 1: Survey of natural gas consumption as well as the process and flue gas temperatures at the site.

Step 2: Estimation of potential savings.

Step 3: Conception of technology integration at the site.

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